

Theoretical Aspects of Neutron Stars by TOV equation

Thein Theint Aung*, Lwun Htet Nay Aung**

Abstract

Attempts have been made to analyze the nature of neutron star with realistic equation of states (EOSs), highly non-linear differential equations, 3+1 numerical relativity and TOV (Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkov) equations. The gravitation potential for their formation are visualized and physical interpretation are given.

Theoretical Background

In 1934, Walter Baade and Fritz Zwicky proposed the existence of neutron star,^[13] only a year after the discovery of the neutron by Sir James Chadwick. In seeking an explanation for the origin of supernova, they tentatively proposed that in supernova explosions ordinary stars are turned into stars that consist of extremely closely packed neutrons that they are called neutron stars.

Neutron star is the remnant core after the supernova explosion of the massive star ($>8M_{\odot}$) at the end of its life. The mass of the neutron star is about solar mass but radii of only 8 to 12 kilometers, and a central density n_c is as high as 5 to 10 times the nuclear density $n_0 \approx 0.16 \text{ fm}^{-3}$ of neutrons and protons found in laboratory nuclei. So neutron stars are the densest objects in the universe. Neutron stars can be detected as radio sources (radio pulsars) or, when they accrete matter coming from a companion star in a binary system.

In order to compute the global structure for neutron star, one has to solve the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff (TOV) equations, which, in the simplified modeling of the star. Important information which can be gathered from solving the TOV equation is the mass-radius relationship for a neutron star given a particular EOS model. The global structure of neutron star is important for understanding of the EOS of matter at supranuclear densities. In practice, this can only be done for neutron stars in the binary system.

The Basics of Neutron Stars Formation

If the mass of the star is high enough in its final stage just before becoming a supernova, it will birth a compact neutron star. The mass of progenitor massive star was between 8 and 25 M_{\odot} and it has the potential to produce a neutron star. The moment of death of massive star is shrunken by the conversion of huge amounts of gravitational binding energy mostly neutrinos (up to ~99% or several 10^{53} ergs). The collapsing of massive star produces plentiful neutrinos to form neutron star. So, newly neutron stars or proto-neutron stars are rich lepton, mostly e^- and ν_e (Fig. 1).

When the inner density of the star reaches nuclear equilibrium density n_0 , core collapse halts, and which triggers the formation of a shock wave generated at the core's outer edges. At that time the inner core is hot and in which neutrinos are trapped [stage I in Fig.1]. The core is surrounded by a low density and high entropy mantle that is both accreting matter from the

* Assistant Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

** Lecturer, Department of Physics, Bago University

outer iron core falling through the shock and also rapidly losing energy due to electron captures and thermal neutrino emission.

The shock wave temporarily halts at around 200 km before the star collapsing. Seemingly, neutrinos from the inner core may be supported by rotation, convection and magnetic fields. Within a few seconds, neutrinos are accelerated and expelling the star, at that time pressure are lost, and then photo-neutron star left after rapidly collapse (stage II). The lepton pressure may loss due the continuously escaping neutrino and deleptonization. Initially the stellar interior is warmed due to the loss of neutrino. Neutrino diffusion deleptonizes the core on time scales of 10–15 s (stage III).

The flow of high-energy (200–300 MeV) neutrinos from the core to the surface where they escape as low-energy neutrinos (10–20 MeV) generates a large amount of heat within the star. The core temperature become over twice and reaching ~ 50 MeV, during this time, and neutrinos continue to be wonderfully emitted from the stars effective surface, known as the ν -sphere. Now the neutron star is poor lepton, but it is still hot. While the star has zero net neutrino number, thermally produced neutrino pairs of all flavors are abundant and dominate the emission. After 10 to 20 s, the steady emission of neutrinos begins to cool the interior, but average neutrino energy decreases, and neutrino mean free path increases. After about 50 s, the star becomes transparent to neutrinos (stage IV).

Following the onset of neutrino transparency, the core continues to cool by neutrino emission, but the star's crust survives warm and cool slowly. The crust is an insulating blanket which prevents the star from coming to complete thermal equilibrium and keeps the surface relatively warm ($T \approx 3 \times 10^6$ K) for up to 100 years (stage V).

For about 10^5 - 10^6 years after their birth in supernova explosions, the temperature of the surface after the interior of the star becomes isothermal (stage VI) is determined by the rate of neutrino emission in the star's core. The rate of magnitude is primarily determined by the question of whether or not one or more of the so-called direct URCA (unrecordable cooling agent) processes can occur.

In some events, ordinary star may survive black hole instead of proto-neutron star due to its early evolution. Since the first stage, this could have two different events. First, the shock fall on the massive star, the star accrete mass. If enough accretion occurs, the star's mass could increase beyond the maximum mass which can support by the hot and lepton-rich matter. If this occurs, the remnant collapses to form a black hole and its neutrino emission would quickly cease. But the accretion terminates when the shock lift off, so proto-neutron star can survive. So in the next events of accretion, the mass of proto-neutron star should have below its maximum mass. In the next stage, when the neutrinos are trapped in the matter, the densities are extremely large. At that time strange matter (hyperons) or quark matter may appear at the end of deleptonization. The decreasing of theoretical maximum mass that matter and the black hole formation are led by the formation of strange matter.

Finally in the evolution of neutron star, firstly the thermal evolution of neutron star must be considered, which is influenced by the weak neutrino emission processes. In the neutron star consisting of nucleons the one-body neutrino emission processes, such as the one-body neutrino-pair processes and the direct URCA (unrecordable cooling agent) process.

Figure. 1 The main stages evolution of a neutron star

Global Structure of Neutron Star

The global structure of a neutron star depends on the equation of state (EOS), i.e. the relation between pressure and density in the neutron star interior. The mechanical structure of neutron star is considered to be spherical. For the spherically symmetric object, the space time by the Schwarzschild metric

$$ds^2 = -e^{2\alpha(r)} dt^2 + e^{2\beta(r)} dr^2 + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \tag{1}$$

where $\alpha(r)$ and $\beta(r)$ are the metric functions depended on the radial coordinate r , t is the time component and r , θ and ϕ are the spatial component,

$$e^{2\beta(r)} = \left(1 - \frac{2Gm(r)}{r}\right)^{-1} \tag{2}$$

and the $\alpha(r)$ can be expected from the following equation;

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dr} = \frac{4\pi Gpr^3 + Gm(r)}{r(r - 2Gm(r))} \tag{3}$$

By taking the boundary condition, $\lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} e^{-2\alpha(r)} = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} e^{2\beta(r)} = 1$

So,

$$e^{2\alpha(r)} = \left(1 - \frac{2Gm(r)}{r}\right) \tag{4}$$

If $r = R_s = 2MG$ the Schwarzschild radius, $m \equiv m(r)$ is star radius, $m(r) = \int_0^r 4\pi r^2 \rho(r) dr$ is mass of the sphere with radius r . Then the structures of spherical symmetric stars are computed utilizing the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff relativistic structure equations (i.e. TOV equations) and detail derivation are given in Appendix A:

$$\frac{dP}{dr} = - \frac{G(m(r) + 4\pi r^3 P)(\rho + P)}{r(r - 2Gm(r))} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dm(r)}{dr} = 4\pi r^2 \rho(r) \quad (6)$$

Where P and ρ are the pressure and mass-energy density, and $m(r)$ is the gravitational mass enclosed within a radius r . This connection is made by the equation of state of matter $P = P(\rho)$ (the set of all spherical symmetric), in particular, an estimate for the maximum mass of the star can be obtained.

These sets of non-linear equations for $p(r)$ and $m(r)$ from $r = 0$ for starting value of $p(r = 0) = p_0$ to the point $r = R$ where the pressure $p(r = R) = 0$. At that point R is the radius of the star. Since $p(r = R) = 0$, it is the vacuum outside of the star because the pressure gradually decreases outwards from the center. So there require that exterior metric should be Schwarzschild metric. Then the metric functions must be continuous at $r = R$:

Inside the star

$$g_{rr} = \left(1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

and outside the star

$$g_{rr} = \left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The total mass of the star is defined as

$$M = m(R) \quad (9)$$

Thus total mass of the star is determined by distant orbits

$$M = \int_0^R 4\pi r^2 \rho(r) dr \quad (10)$$

Outside the distribution of mass, which terminates at the radius of star R , there is in vacuum with $p(r = R) = 0$ and Einstein equations give

$$g_{00}(r = R) = -\left(1 - \frac{2M}{r}\right) \quad (11)$$

Figure 2. 3D variation of the gradient of mass $\frac{dm}{dr}$ with radius r and density ρ

Figure 3. 3D variation of the gravitational potential inside the star g_{rr} with radius r and mass m (It includes singular points)

Figure 4. 3D variation of the gravitational potential outside the star g_{tt} with radius r and mass m

Figure 5. 3D variation of gradient of pressure $\frac{dP}{dR}$ with radius r and pressure P

If the maximum mass is not relatively small, the radius is relatively determined to the mass in the near of 1 to $1.5M_{\odot}$ for the neutron star. An intermediate mass star's radius and mass could help to distinguish from the group of possible EOS's. The two most important of the astrophysical quantities are the neutron star maximum mass and the radius of $1.4 M_{\odot}$ neutron star. Between neutron star and nuclear matter have the important fact that is their proton fraction x . Number of proton and neutron are mostly equal in nuclear matter ($x \approx \frac{1}{2}$), but proton are a few percent in the neutron star. The composition of β -stable matter of density n_0 is found by minimization of the energy of charge neutral nucleon matter with leptonic contribution with respect to proton fraction. The energy per nucleon distribution is

$$E(n, x) = E(n, x=1/2) + S_v(n)(1-2x)^2 \quad (12)$$

where $E(n, x=1/2)$ is the energy of symmetric nuclear matter at density n and $S_v(n)$ is the symmetry energy at n . If $S_v(n) < 0$, the minimum of the total energy occurs at some finite proton fraction $x \neq 0$. However, when $S_v(n) = 0$, the minimum occurs at $x = 0$. This means that the density n corresponds to vanishing of the symmetry energy, $S_v(n)$. The symmetry energy is negative, $S_v(n) > 0$.

A potential constraint on the EOS derives from the rotation of neutron stars. An absolute upper limit to the neutron star spin frequency is the mass-shedding limit, at which the velocity of the stellar surface equals that of an orbiting particle suspended just above the surface. For a rigid Newtonian sphere this frequency is the Keplerian rate:

$$\nu = (2\pi)^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R^3}} \quad (13)$$

Both deformation and GR effects are important and in which M and R refer to the mass and radius of the maximum mass, non-rotating, configuration, describes the maximum rotation rate possible for an EOS.

Concluding Remarks

Using general relativity, one can derive the TOV equations and the nature of gravitational potentials can be then determined. If $r > R_s$, where r is the radius of star, and $R_s = 2MG$, i.e., the Schwarzschild radius, with the mass of the star M and the gravitational constant G . For $r < R_s$, the star becomes unstable and connected with gravitational collapse and likely to form a black hole. The 3-D variation of the gradient of the mass $\frac{dm}{dr}$ can be visualized in terms of radial function r and density ρ . Then, the 3D variation of the gravitational potential g_r can be visualized in terms of radial function r and mass m and the 3D variation of the gravitational potential g_{tt} can be visualized in terms of radial function r and mass m . When the radius of the star reached the Schwarzschild radius R_s , neutron star has infinite gravity and that point is called singularity.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Aye AyeTun, Rector, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this research. I would like to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this research. I would like to express my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Khin Mar Ohn, Head of Department of Physics, Bago University, for her kind permission to carry out this research. I wish to show my sincere thanks to Professor Dr Khin Htoo, Department of Physics, Bago University, for her encouragement to carry out this research. Special thanks are due to Professor Dr Thant ZinNaing, Retired Pro-Rector (Admin), International Theravāda Buddhist Missionary University, for his valuable guidance and helpful advice to carry out this work.

References

- AaronSmith. (2012). *“Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff (TOV) Stars”*. Department of Astronomy, The University of Texas at Austin, Austin.
- Faber Joshua A & Rasio Frederic A. (2012). *“Binary Neutron Star Mergers”*. Department of Physics and Astronomy, Northwestern University, USA.
- Friedman J. L, Parker L, Ipser J R. (1986). *“Rapidly Rotating Neutron Stars Model”*. AstrophysicsJournal. J. 304, 115, Department of Physics, University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee & University of Florida, USA.
- Hernquist, L. (1990). *“An analytical model for spherical galaxies and bulges”*. ApJ.
- Lattimer J. M &Pethick C J. (2004). *“The Physics of Neutron Stars”*, Department of Physics & Astronomy, State University of New York at Stony Brook, USA.
- Lattimer J. M &Pethick M, Masak D., Yahil A. (1990). *“Rapidly Rotating Pulsars and the Equation of States”*. AJ, J. 355, 241.
- Maccio” A. V., Stinson G., Brook C. B., Wadsley J., Couchman H. M. P., Shen S., Gibson B.K., Quinn T., (2012). ApJ.
- Manchester N, Taylor J.H. (1977). *“Pulsars”*. Irish Astronomical Journal.
- Nice et al. (2005). *“Solar Mass Pulsar Measured by Relativistic Orbital Decay”*. Astrophysics Journal.
- PrakashMadappa, Lattimer James M, Pons Jose A., Steiner Andrew W, and Reddy Sanjay. (2000). *“Evolution of a Neutron Star from its Birth to Old Age”*. Department of Physics & Astronomy, State University of New York, Institute for Nuclear Theory, University of Washington, USA.
- Zwicky, Fritz & Baade, Walter. (1934). *“Remarks on Super-Novae and Cosmic Rays”*. Physics Review 46.